

TWO CULTURES: DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF THE UZBEK-ENGLISH WEDDING CEREMONY

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Annotation: *In this scientific work, the similarities and differences of the national-cultural traditions of the Uzbek-English wedding ceremonies related to marriage will be discussed.*

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Wherever you go in the world, you will find a culture rich in traditions. It is part of the human experience to pass on these images to the next generation, and to create such rituals and traditions in order to "keep in touch" with the ancestors. Every culture has its own traditions, sometimes their intimacy is unique and warm, but often they are mysterious and incomprehensible to people of other cultures.

So, according to the customs of the British nation, what wedding traditions are similar or different from Uzbek wedding ceremonies? The main customs of the English wedding are as follows: In England, there is a ceremony of sprinkling rice and sweets on the young people after the church. Previously, it was sprinkled only on the bride, not after the wedding. At Uzbek weddings, the bride and groom are sprinkled with sugar. I mean, let their lives be as sweet as sugar.

A girl walks next to the bride and helps her in everything. It's very similar to our so-called "girlfriend" (in some regions "bride-in-law") witness at the time of marriage, isn't it? It is also common for the bridegroom to take off his shoes and throw them in the groom's basket during the celebration. The bride, as if on her way to the wedding, accidentally "loses" her bouquet. And the friends of the bridegroom, having found it, solemnly search around the church. Throwing bouquets to girls is also an old custom. By now, instead of a bouquet, the bride throws pieces of cake into the crowd of guests. In the past, sweets were ceremonially "poured" on the bride's head, but now many people have abandoned this tradition. Another wedding tradition in England is that all newlyweds, regardless of the social status of the young family, must go on a trip after the wedding.

But there's one thing people dread about an English wedding? As in Russia, May is not considered the most suitable month for a holiday. But according to popular beliefs, rain, which brings prosperity to newlyweds for Uzbeks, is considered a bad sign in England. It is also believed that misfortune awaits young people who enter the church under the sound of the city clock. Therefore, at such a time, the newlyweds always wait outside. At Uzbek weddings, the bride and groom enter the wedding hall with special songs, and trumpets are played before their arrival.

Another bad old sign comes from Ireland. A stone rolled in front of a wedding procession can bring misfortune. In Uzbeks, a black cat is the cause of such a situation. But the interesting fact is that a little girl running to the church in front of the groom is considered a good sign. If you are planning a wedding in England, these signs can play a big role for those around you. But before the wedding ceremony, the British also have special preparations.

To the bride going to the church (today brides prefer to go to the church, instead of going to the church), the crowd scatters flower petals. According to the customs of Uzbek weddings, the bride enters the wedding hall together with the groom and greets her parents before sitting at the table, after which the main party begins. After the English wedding ceremony, a photo session with all the guests is organized immediately. As a rule, group photos are taken near the church where the couple got married. But if the weather outside is bad, photography is allowed inside the church walls. At Uzbek weddings, the bride and groom are photographed in a photo studio before the wedding ceremony, and during the wedding, souvenir photos are taken.

In England, wedding presents are usually not opened until the end of the honeymoon. And when the presents are opened, the newlyweds send thank-you notes to the guests. Among the Uzbeks, it is a common custom to give "to'yona" to the bride and groom. These "to'yona" are given to the bride's father and mother by their relatives on the wedding day. It is given to the bride and groom at the table where they are sitting, and sometimes it can be presented to the bride and groom as a "souvenir" when they go to the bride's house after the wedding.

In the UK, it is customary to have a 'bachelorette party' with close friends before the wedding. For men, it's called a "Single night" or something similar. According to one of its types, the concept of this night originally came from the Roman Empire, from where it moved to Britain, and was originally called "the last supper in celibacy". And Uzbek grooms organize a dinner party for their friends on the day before the wedding.

The English believe that the best day to connect two hearts is Wednesday. And in some regions, the cake baking ceremony is very popular among brides. Brides prepare a cake made of flour and water. Happy brides eat it at night, eat and sleep. The main

emphasis in this "pie baking" ceremony is that the bride should not talk to anyone after eating.

The best choice for a wedding dress is white, according to the customs of the two nations. There are opinions that it was the representatives of the English royal family who introduced this color of the shirt. At an English wedding, it is very important to tie a horseshoe to the dress, which they believe brings great luck. Also, this custom is a very ancient tradition that goes back many centuries, and Princess Diana, who married Prince Charles, did not ignore it.

The bouquet for the bride is made of red roses, which in turn is an integral symbol of England. The groom who brings a bouquet to Uzbek brides prepares it according to his desire, taste and flowers that the bride likes. Accessories with symbols of the nation and a cap invented by the British are chosen for the groom. Uzbek grooms wear a suit-trousers for the wedding hall, a groom's coat with a belt tied around the waist when the bride is taken down, and a hat.

The scenario of the wedding in the church is a mandatory task of the registry office of the English wedding. According to him, the registry office will bring all wedding participants, guests, parents and newlyweds by train. When the train goes to the registry office, specially hired and "told" people throw fresh flowers and firearms in the air. It is believed that these sounds scare away evil spirits. At Uzbek weddings, guests are called by the hosts of the wedding when they go to drop off the bride in a new house. Everyone visits the wedding hall and the bride and groom enter the wedding hall to the sounds of national or modern Uzbek music.

In English custom, when the bride is led into the hall by the groom's father, a little girl comes before him and sprinkles fresh flowers on the way. Newlyweds take a vow of loyalty to each other to the sounds of wonderful music, and then more interesting events begin. Before the wedding reception, small bags with the names of the guests and sweets, business cards are placed on the tables, and the guests are thanked by the newlyweds. In Uzbeks, this situation is completely different. The bride's father-in-law does not bring the bride to the wedding hall, the oath is not read, on the contrary, during the marriage ceremony, which is read before the wedding, they agree to each other's mahram. Writing the names of the guests on the wedding table is a custom found in some weddings.

The menu of the wedding reception is created in great variety and is characterized by assortments. Among the wedding dishes are baked lamb, alcohol - champagne, wine and various sweets and fruits. A wedding cake is the main menu item for a wedding reception. The bride and groom cut it independently and share it among the invited guests, but keep the upper part for themselves. According to the rules, the last part is

given to her husband's friends, which means that they will start a family soon. After the cakes are eaten, the first dance after the wedding meal should be performed by a friend of the groom. In the sequel, everyone goes for a walk together, after which fire dances are organized. These traditions are similar to those of the Uzbeks. Because at present, the bride and groom waltz, cutting a special cake in the middle of the stage, and "love story" are customs that came from the European mentality. After that, the groom's party begins, the groomsmen bring the groom to the center, make a circle and have fun. Thus, a unique culture is evident in English-Uzbek wedding ceremonies.

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